

1. Percent increase in total dry weight of rice at maturity for doubled CO₂ (840 ppm) treatment over the ambient CO₂ control as a function of N rate and temperature averaged over the growth period. Pot experiment, 1990.

2. Relative responses of crop dry weight at maturity under doubled CO₂ as a function of N level. Vertical bars indicate the standard deviation calculated using the data obtained under 4 temperature regimes.

Increase in crop dry weight by doubling CO₂ was higher at higher N and higher temperatures due to increases in both leaf area and photosynthetic rate.

CO₂ effects on plants in a community. The results obtained in 1991 and 1992, when plants were maintained under canopy conditions, were different from the results with single plants. No consistent trend could be seen in the temperature effects on rice response to the elevated CO₂ under canopy conditions, as was reported in an earlier study (Horie

1993). The average values of relative increases in crop dry weight by doubling CO₂ across temperature treatments as a function of N application rate were plotted in Figure 2. The relative increase was greater at higher N levels and reached a maximum at around 24 g N/m². CO₂ had little effect on leaf area at heading for all N × temperature plots. The enhancement rates of crop dry weight at maturity obtained from pot experiments were much lower than those of field experiments.

When collecting data to assess impact of global climate change on the rice crop, experiments should be done under canopy conditions and underground environments similar to those of field conditions. By analyzing data from long-term CO₂ enrichment experiments on rice, which satisfy these conditions (our TGT experiments and Baker et al 1990), Horie (1993) concluded that the relative increase in rice dry weight by doubling CO₂ was

24%, being less affected by temperature. Our analysis indicates that this enhancement in total dry weight by doubling CO₂ increases with increased N levels up to 30% at optimum N level.

REFERENCES CITED

- Baker J T, Allen L H Jr, Boote J K, Rowland-Bamford A J, Waschmann R S, Jones J W, Jones P H, Bowes G (1990) 1989 Progress report of response to vegetation to carbon dioxide. Report No. 060 Plant Stress and Protection Research Unit, USDA-ARS, University of Florida, Gainesville. 70 p.
- Horie T, Nakano J, Nakagawa H, Wada K, Kim H Y, Seo T (1991). J. Crop Sci. 60 (Extra issue 2): 127-128.
- Horie T (1993) J. Agric. Meteorol. 48(5):567-574.
- Imai K, Coleman D F, Yanagisawa T (1985) Increase in atmospheric partial pressure of carbon dioxide and growth and yield of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). Jpn. J. Crop Sci. 54(4):413-418.
- Kimbal B A (1983) Agron. J. 75:779-788. ■

Responses of rice to elevated levels of carbon dioxide

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Rice is the major crop in China in terms of cultivated area and total yield. The aim of this study was to determine the effects of elevated levels of CO₂ concentration on a Chinese rice variety, Aixiangnuo, and to generate basic parameters for developing global change-crop reaction models.

The experiments were conducted at the Botanical Garden of the Institute of Botany in 1993-94. Ambient or CO₂-enriched (plus 350 ppm CO₂) air was introduced through the bottom of cylindrical open-top chambers (2.2 m diam × 1.7 m tall) with aluminum frames

covered by polyethylene film. Ventilation rate of the chamber was maintained at 3 exchanges/min throughout the growing season. Rice was planted in fertile soil in pots (25 cm diameter × 30 cm tall), and a 3-5 cm water depth was maintained.

The dry matter partitioning in the young seedlings under elevated CO₂ levels was measured (Table 1). Total dry weight increased by 15%, compared with seedlings grown under ambient atmospheric condition. Shoot dry weight increased only 4%, but with the major increase in dry matter occurring in the roots. Elevated CO₂ influences C metabolism and dry matter partitioning between shoots and roots in the rice plant even at early growth stages.

Elevated CO₂ also affected growth at maturity: compared with the control,

Table 1. Influences of CO₂ enrichment on dry matter (mg) partitioning between shoots and roots in 3-4 leaf stage rice seedlings.

Treatment	Whole seedling		Shoot		Root		Root:Shoot	
	Dry weight (g)	(%)	Dry weight (g)	(%)	Dry weight (g)	(%)	Ratio	(%)
Ambient air	24.7	100	18.4	100	6.3	100	0.34	100
Ambient air plus 350 ppm CO ₂	28.5	115	19.1	104	9.4	149	0.49	

Table 2. Effects of elevated CO₂ level on the growth of rice at maturity and on the reproductive characteristics of rice.

Treatment	Culm length (cm)	Root dry weight (g/plant)	Shoot dry weight (g/Plant)	Root-shoot ratio	Grain yield (t/plant)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	1,000 grain weight (g)
Ambient air	61.35 ± 0.9	1.63 ± 0.35	6.52 ± 0.92	0.25	6.35 ± 0.31	3.8 ± 0.2	52.7 ± 1.6	31.7 ± 0.8
Ambient plus 350 ppm CO ₂	68.4 ± 1.1	2.00 ± 0.24	6.47 ± 0.61	0.31	8.98 ± 0.41	3.9 ± 0.1	67.9 ± 1.4	33.9 ± 1.0
± (%)	+ 11.8	+ 23.0	- 0.7	+ 24	+ 41.4	+ 2.6	- 28.8	+ 6.9

plant culm length increased by 11.8%, root dry weight increased by 23%, and root-shoot ratio increased by 24%. Almost no change in shoot dry weight was observed (Table 2).

Grain yield per plant increased by 41.4% under elevated CO₂ levels. Increases in filled grains per panicle and 1,000-grain weight contributed to the higher yield. No significant change in panicles per plant occurred (Table 2).

Results of this study are similar to those of previous studies (Imai et al 1986,

Baker et al 1990, Ziska and Teramura 1992). Baker et al (1990), using IR30, observed that panicle number per plant was almost entirely responsible for differences in final grain yield among CO₂ treatments. Doubling the CO₂ concentration from 330 to 660 ppm resulted in a 32% increase in grain yield. Ziska and Teramura (1992) described differences in reproductive characteristics between IR36 and Fujiyama 5 cultivars. Considering the large diversity of growth and developmental properties in different

rice cultivars, more cultivars need to be studied under elevated CO₂.

REFERENCES CITED

Baker J T, Allen L H, Jr., Boote J K (1990) Growth and yield responses of rice to carbon dioxide concentration. *J. Agric. Sci.* 115:313-320.
 Iami K, Coleman D F, Yanagisawa T (1985) *Jpn. J. Crop Sci.* 54:413-418.
 Ziska L H, Teramura A (1997) *Physiol. Plant.* 84:269-276. ■

Modeling leaf and canopy photosynthesis of rice in response to carbon dioxide and temperature

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Model equations were developed to predict leaf and canopy assimilation of rice as a function of CO₂, temperature, photosynthetic active radiation (PAR), time of day, leaf traits, and canopy leaf area index (LAI) as described by Boote and Pickering (1984). Predictions were compared with canopy assimilation measured on rice grown in sunlit, controlled-environment chambers under season-long treatments of CO₂ and temperature (Baker et al 1990, 1992). Apparent assimilation, CO₂, air temperature, and PAR were recorded at 5-min intervals throughout the day.

The model accounts for diffuse and direct beam interception of PAR, computes irradiance on sunlit and shaded leaf classes, and computes photosynthesis of sunlit and shaded leaf classes with asymptotic exponential equations (Boote and Pickering 1994). Temperature and CO₂ effects on quantum efficiency (QE)

1. Gross assimilation vs photosynthetic active radiation (PAR) at 160,330, and 660 vpm CO₂.

and light saturated leaf photosynthesis (P_{max}) are computed using equations 16.60 a, b of Farquhar and von Caemmerer (1982), assuming limiting RuBP and temperature effects on the specificity factor of rubisco for CO₂ vs O₂. The equations are scaled to a QE of 0.0541 mol/mol and a relative effect of 1.0 P_{max} at 30 °C and 350 vpm CO₂. Actual QE and P_{max} depend on intercellular CO₂ concentration (C_i), temperature, and oxygen.

2. Gross assimilation vs temperature at 350 or 700 vpm CO₂.

The canopy assimilation model was used with nonlinear regression to solve for single leaf P_{max} for individual rice canopies grown at a range of CO₂ levels and temperatures. For these regressions, we entered observed LAI, and 5-min averages of CO₂, air temperature, and PAR measured throughout the day for each chamber. Measured plants were 60 d old and LAI ranged from 5 to 11 in the two experiments. A spherical leaf angle distribution was assumed.